

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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The coronation and campaigns of Alexander The Great

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Abstract: in this article, we will dwell on the process of coming to power of Alexander Makedonsky, who is recognized as the first Jahangir in history, having a special place in the history of the ancient world, and the wars that the activities of his military campaigns took especially to Central Asia.

Key words: Philip II, Alexander, Achaemenid, Darius III, Arrian, Quintus Curtius Ruf, Jaxart-Syrdarya, Ochs, Bess, Maraqand, Khwarazm, Choch (Tashkent Oasis), Fergana, land of SACS, Sughdiyona, Bactria, Marghiyona, Parthia

Today, the unique management system of the Uzbek statehood has been formed over the long millennia, and as a result of various invasions, it has passed the test. It would not be a mistake to say that one of the first roots of these processes was the Greek-Macedonian campaigns of invasion and the policy of governance that accompanied the economic, cultural Hellenistic processes that they left in the life of our country is also considered an example of early governance. Philip II of Macedon died suddenly during the campaigns of the invasion. The throne is held by his 20-year-old son Alexander. From historians, Arrian, reflecting on Alexander, can see that he was highly appreciated by him: "Alexander The Great was a brave commander, and the Just King was, at the same time, an ideal man who knew his perfection." He seriously entered the war against the Achaemenids and summoned the

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Parmenionic chieftain troops from Asia Minor. The military council set clear tasks for the troops acting on the dust and water.

Mil. in the 1st century BC. In May 334 (next to the Graniq River), in October 333 (in Gavgamela, northeastern Mesopotamia), Persian forces suffered a complete defeat. After that, the road to the Centers of the Achaemenid state was opened for Alexander. Alexander first captured Babylon, and then the treasures of the Persian tsars, occupying the cities of Suza, Persepolis, Pasargada. The last Achaemenid ruler, Darius III, fled first to the Medes and then to Bactria. According to cursius Rufus, Bactria was assassinated in a conspiracy against Darius III, and Bess, who led the plot, proclaimed himself King of the Achaemenids. Bess, however, was unable to counter Alexander with military troops.

Historian N. According to Khlopin I. Zulqarnain's March to Central Asia is in the following 4 stages:

1. Medea-Gircan invasion.(mil.in the 1st century BC.333 BC).
2. Aryan and Drangian invasions.(mil.in the 1st century BC.329 BC).
3. Bactria and the Sogdian invasion.(mil.in the 1st century BC.328 BC).
4. Sogdian and Indian invasion.(mil.in the 1st century BC.327 BC) can be seen to have carried out.

Mil. in the 1st century BC. By the spring of 329, Alexander was occupying regions such as Aria, Drangiyona, Arachosia, and coming out into the Axis powers. According to Arrian and cursive Ruf at this time, the river was very succulent and overflowed. Alexander's troops, after crossing the river in pursuit of Bess, head for the “Sughd region of Navtaka” (first the Advanced section under Ptolemy Lag, then the main force). In the Sugd lands, the Spitaman Chief local warlords take Bess hostage and hand him over in an

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attempt to stop Alexander. Alexander, however, had no intention of stopping military campaigns. After navtaka, Greco-Macedonian troops march on Smarakanda, the capital of Sugdiyona, and take it. According to the Italic Ruf, the Greco-Macedonians begin to move towards the northeast, “leaving behind their small gornizons in the city, burning and destroying nearby villages”. In the mountainous regions between Jizzakh and O'ratepa, the Greco-Macedonian armies experience severe casualties. Alexander himself is badly wounded. Nevertheless, the Greco-Macedonian steppe nomads, who barely defeated the inhabitants of the mountainous region, move towards Yaksart-Syrdaryoga, which forms the border between the sacs and Sughdians. The Greco-Macedonians stopped by the Bank of Jakarta and began to place their military units in the cities here. Soon the inhabitants of these cities raise an uprising against Alexander. The Saks on the Right Bank of the river also begin to gather their troops together. At the same time, uprisings against Alexander began in the regions of Bactria and Sughdiyona.

Alexander at first decided to strengthen his position on the banks of Jakarta, suppressing the uprisings here. In sughdiyona, A.D.in the 1st century BC. In autumn 329, he dispatched troops under the command of sarkarda Farnoux to suppress an uprising (at Marocand) led by Spitaman. He himself marched on the Saks with the main forces. However, this march ended without attitude.

The troops sent to Marocanda under farnoux were defeated by Spitaman. Alexander himself was forced to return to Sughdiyona with his main forces. The rebels had been hiding in areas in the mountainous regions of sugdiana where the invaders had not reached the mark. Almost all the inhabitants of sugdiyana sided with Spitaman and had high hopes for his victories. Alexander, however, died in 1700 BC.in the 1st century BC. He did not waste

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time spending the winter of 329-328 in Bactria (some sources say in Navtaka). Here he negotiated with the Khwarezmian ruler Farasman. As a result, Alexander's plan to march on Khorezm was abandoned.

Mil. in the 1st century BC. From the spring of 328, the struggle against the Greco-Macedonians was again in full swing. Local residents continued to fight in large cities, castles, mountainous areas. Alarmed by the seriousness of the situation, Alexander divided his 30,000 troops into 5 groups, which he placed in charge of the trusted warlords, Hephaestion, Ptolemy Lag, Perdikkas, Ken, and Artaboz. The forces were unequal. In this struggle, after the death of Spitaman, mainly mountain fortresses turn into riot foci. These include “Sugd rock” (or “Arimaz rock”), “Horien rock”, mentioned in written sources.

The indigenous people who lived in the regions of Uzbekistan have acted as a recognition-a soul for their freedom and independence. However, the ratio of forces and unequal military equipment in many cases ensured the superiority of the invaders. Nevertheless, such cases have left an important mark on the history of statehood.

Thus the Land of Khorezm, Choch (Tashkent Oasis), Fergana and Sakas will remain independent of Alexander. Sugdonia, Bactria, Marghiona and Parthia were added to Alexander's state, and later some Greek-Macedonian States would form on their territory.

References:

- 1.Eshov B O'zbekiston davlatchiligi va boshqaruv tarixi.-T.: “O'zbekiston Milliy Universitet”, 2012
- 2.Usmonov Q, Sodiqov M, Oblomurodov N O'zbekiston tarixi.- T.: “Abdulla Qodiriy “, 2002
- 3.Boynazorov F Qadimgi dunyo tarixi.- T.: “Iqtisod-Moliya”, 2006

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SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 5, 31 Май

4. Jo'rayev U , Usmonov Q, Norqulov A Tarixdan hikoyalar.- T.: “Cho'lpon”, 2011
5. Muyiddinov, B. (2023). XII-XIII ASRLAR DAVRIDA BUXORODA ILM – FANNING RIVOJLANISHI. SCHOLAR, 1(28), 341–345. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10027071>
6. Muyiddinov Bekali. (2023). MO'G'ULLAR BOSQINI DAVRIDA BUXORONING AYANCHLI TAQDIRI. TADQIQOTLAR, 25(2), 212–215. Retrieved from <http://tadqiqotlar.uz/index.php/new/article/view/308>
7. Muyiddinov Bekali. (2023). THE ROLE OF BUKHARA AND OTHER CITIES IN THE MILITARY ART AND ARMY STRUCTURE OF KHOREZMSHAHS . ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 35(3), 55–58. Retrieved from <https://www.newjournal.org/index.php/01/article/view/10035>
8. Muyiddinov Bekali. (2024). BARTOLDNING “СОЧИНЕНИЯ. ТОМ I. ТУРКЕСТАН В ЭПОХУ МОНГОЛЬСКОГО НАШЕСТВИЯ” ASARINING YARALISH TARIXI. 25(2), 699–702. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10552555>
9. Muyiddinov Bekali. (2024). SHAYBONIYLAR DAVRIDA BUXORO XONLIGIDA HARBIY ISLOHOTLARNING DAVLAT HAYOTIDA TUTGAN O'RNI. International Journal Of History And Political Sciences, 3(11), 646–648. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10668887>
10. Muyiddinov Bekali. (2024). Military Art of Turkish Khaganate in the Early Middle Ages. European Journal of Innovation in Nonformal Education (EJINE), 4(3), 223–227. <https://inovatus.es/index.php/ejine/article/view/2705/2586>
11. Бобохусенов, А. (2024). ИСТОРИЧЕСКАЯ ГЕОГРАФИЯ БУХАРСКОГО ОАЗИСА. СОВРЕМЕННАЯ НАУКА И

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Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 5, 31 Май

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ, 3(2), 634–640.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10667247>

12. Бобохусенов, А., и Ганиев, Х. (2024). ПРОБЛЕМЫ ПРОИСХОЖДЕНИЯ САКСКОЙ АРХЕОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ. СОВРЕМЕННАЯ НАУКА И ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ, 3(2), 641–645.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10667306>

13. Akmal , B. (2024). THE GREAT WALL OF THE EARLY MIDDLE AGES - KANPIRAK WALL. Modern Science and Research, 3(1), 694–698. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/scienceresearch/article/view/28381>

14. Bobohusenov Akmal. (2023). BUXORO VOHSINING ANTIK DAVRI SHISHA BUYUMLARI. TADQIQOTLAR, 25(2), 208–211. Retrieved from <http://tadqiqotlar.uz/index.php/new/article/view/307>

15. Bobohusenov Akmal Ashurovich. (2023). THE MATERIAL CULTURE OF THE TOMBS OF THE ANCIENT AND EARLY MEDIEVAL PERIOD. International Journal Of History And Political Sciences, 3(11), 24–29. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ijhps/Volume03Issue11-06>

16. Bobohusenov Akmal. (2023). ANTIK VA ILK OʻRTA ASRLAR DAVRI MOZOR QOʻRGʻONLARI MODDIY MADANIYATI. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 35(3), 65–70. Retrieved from <https://www.newjournal.org/index.php/01/article/view/10037>

17. Bobohusenov Akmal. (2023). ANTIK VA ILK OʻRTA ASRLAR DAVRI MOZOR QOʻRGʻONLARI MODDIY MADANIYATI. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 35(3),

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Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 5, 31 Май

65–70. Retrieved from

<https://www.newjournal.org/index.php/01/article/view/10037>

18. Tursunova, M., & Bobohusenov, A. (2023). QADIMGI VARAXSHA DEVORIY GANCH VA LOY BEZAKLARI. SCHOLAR, 1(28), 303–308.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10026873>

19. Bobohusenov Akmal. (2023). BUXORO VOHSINING ANTIK DAVRI SHISHA BUYUMLARI. TADQIQOTLAR, 25(2), 208–211.

Retrieved from <http://tadqiqotlar.uz/index.php/new/article/view/307>

20. Bobohusenov Akmal Ashurovich. (2023). VARAKHSHA MURAL GANCH AND CLAY PAINTINGS. International Journal of History and Political Sciences, 3(12), 48–53.

<https://doi.org/10.37547/ijhps/Volume03Issue12-09>

21. Bobohusenov Akmal, & Naimov Ismat. (2023). BAQTRIYANING BRONZA DAVRI ARXEOLOGIYA YODGORLIKLARINING JOYLASHUVI VA MODDIY MADANIYATI. Innovations in Technology and Science Education, 2(8), 73–80. Retrieved from

<https://humoscience.com/index.php/itse/article/view/557>

22. YODGORLIKLARI. SCHOLAR, 1(28), 298–302. Retrieved from <https://researchedu.org/index.php/openscholar/article/view/5055>

23. Bobohusenov Akmal. (2023). BUXORO VOHASI QOYATOSH SURATLARINING DAVRIY TASNIFI. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 29(1), 142–146. Retrieved from <https://newjournal.org/index.php/01/article/view/8667>

24. Shokir o‘g‘li, S. U. (2023). MAHALLANING JAMIYAT IJTIMOIIY TARAQQIYOTIDAGI O‘RNI. Научный Фокус, 1(6), 369-371.

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Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 5, 31 Май

25. Shokir o'g'li, S. U. (2024). MIRZO SIROJ HAKIM VA UNING MEROSI.

26. Sadullayev , U. (2024). MIRZA SIROJ HAKIM AND HIS LEGACY. Modern Science and Research, 3(2), 902–910. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/29502>

27. Sadullayev, U. . (2024). THE NEIGHBORHOOD IS THE CRADLE OF VALUES. Modern Science and Research, 3(1), 607–613. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/scienceresearch/article/view/28343>

28. Sadullayev, U. (2023). ABOUT THE EMERGENCE OF THE CONCEPT OF

NEIGHBORHOOD. Modern Science and Research, 2(12), 722-727.

29. Sadullayev Umidjon Shokir O'g'li. (2023). THE IMPORTANCE OF THE MAHALLA SYSTEM'S REFORMATIONS IN NEW UZBEKISTAN. International Journal Of History And Political Sciences, 3(10), 25–30. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ijhps/Volume03Issue10-05>

30. Sadullayev Umidjon Shokir o'g'li. (2023). The History of the Creation and Formation of the Neighborhood. American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education (2993-2769), 1(10), 480–485. Retrieved from <https://grnjournal.us/index.php/STEM/article/view/2142>

31. O'g'li, S. U. S. (2023). ELUCIDATION OF ISSUES OF THE HISTORY OF BUKHARA GUZARS IN OA SUKHAREVA AND HER STUDIES. International Journal Of History And Political Sciences, 3(11), 30-35.

32. Sadullayev, U. (2023). ABOUT THE EMERGENCE OF THE CONCEPT OF NEIGHBORHOOD. Modern Science and Research, 2(12), 722–727.

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 5, 31 Май

33. Shokir o'g'li, S. U. (2023). The Essence of State Policy on Youth in New Uzbekistan. American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education (2993-2769), 1(9), 554-559.
34. Sadullayev, U. (2023). THE ROLE OF THE NEIGHBORHOOD IN RAISING A SPIRITUALLY MATURE GENERATION. Modern Science and Research, 2(10), 488-493.
35. Sadullayev, U. (2023). O'zbekistonda xotin-qizlarga berilayotgan e'tibor: mahalla boshqaruvida xotin-qizlarning roli. In Oriental Conferences (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 551-556). ООО 'SupportScience'.
36. Sadullayev, U. (2023). THE ROLE OF THE NEIGHBORHOOD IN THE SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY. Modern Science and Research, 2(10), 755-757.
37. Shokir o'g'li, U. S. (2023). MILLIY QADRIYATLARIMIZ ASROVCHISI. Journal of new century innovations, 35(1), 79-80.
38. Sadullayev, U. (2023). THE ROLE OF WOMEN IN NEIGHBORHOOD MANAGEMENT IN UZBEKISTAN. Modern Science and Research, 2(9), 132-135.
39. Sayfutdinov, F. (2024). HISTORIOGRAPHY OF INFORMATION ABOUT THE POPULATION OF THE ZARAFSHAN OASIS.(20TH CENTURY). Modern Science and Research, 3(2), 911-914.
40. Shokir o'g'li, S. U. (2023). MAHALLA TUSHUNCHASINING VUJUDGA KELISHI HAQIDA.
41. Shokir o'g'li, S. U. (2024). MIRZO SIROJ HAKIM VA UNING MEROSI.
42. Shokir o'g'li, S. U. (2024). Media literacy is a requirement of the modern world. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION, 4(3), 276-280.

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Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 5, 31 Май

43. Sadullayev, U. (2024). THE CONCEPT OF JADIDISM AND ITS ESSENCE. Modern Science and Research, 3(2), 631–636. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/30324>
44. Shokir o'g'li, S. U. (2023). MAHALLANING JAMIYAT IJTIMOIIY TARAQQIYOTIDAGI O'RNI. Научный Фокус, 1(6), 369-371.
45. Sadullayev, U. (2024). MIRZA SIROJ HAKIM AND HIS LEGACY. Modern Science and Research, 3(2), 902–910. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/29502>
46. Sadullayev, U. . (2024). THE NEIGHBORHOOD IS THE CRADLE OF VALUES. Modern Science and Research, 3(1), 607–613. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/28343>
47. Sadullayev, U. (2023). ABOUT THE EMERGENCE OF THE CONCEPT OF NEIGHBORHOOD. Modern Science and Research, 2(12), 722-727.
48. Sadullayev Umidjon Shokir O'g'li. (2023). THE IMPORTANCE OF THE MAHALLA SYSTEM'S REFORMATIONS IN NEW UZBEKISTAN. International Journal Of History And Political Sciences, 3(10), 25–30. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ijhps/Volume03Issue10-05>
49. Sadullayev Umidjon Shokir o'g'li. (2023). The History of the Creation and Formation of the Neighborhood. American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education (2993-2769), 1(10), 480–485. Retrieved from <https://grnjournal.us/index.php/STEM/article/view/2142>
50. O'gli, S. U. S. (2023). ELUCIDATION OF ISSUES OF THE HISTORY OF BUKHARA GUZARS IN OA SUKHAREVA AND HER STUDIES. International Journal Of History And Political Sciences, 3(11), 30-35.
51. Sadullayev, U. (2023). ABOUT THE EMERGENCE OF THE CONCEPT OF NEIGHBORHOOD. Modern Science and Research, 2(12), 722–727.

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Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 5, 31 Май

52. Shokir o'gli, S. U. (2023). The Essence of State Policy on Youth in New Uzbekistan. *American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education* (2993-2769), 1(9), 554-559.
53. Sadullayev, U. (2023). THE ROLE OF THE NEIGHBORHOOD IN RAISING A SPIRITUALLY MATURE GENERATION. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 488-493.
54. Sadullayev, U. (2023). O'zbekistonda xotin-qizlarga berilayotgan e'tibor: mahalla boshqaruvida xotin-qizlarning roli. In *Oriental Conferences* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 551-556). ООО «SupportScience».
55. Sadullayev, U. (2023). THE ROLE OF THE NEIGHBORHOOD IN THE SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 755-757.
56. Shokir o'gli, U. S. (2023). MILLIY QADRIYATLARIMIZ ASROVCHISI. *Journal of new century innovations*, 35(1), 79-80.
57. Sadullayev, U. (2023). THE ROLE OF WOMEN IN NEIGHBORHOOD MANAGEMENT IN UZBEKISTAN. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 132-135.
58. Shokir o'g'li, S. U. (2024). Media literacy is a requirement of the modern world. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 4(3), 276-280.
59. Sadullayev, U. (2024). EDWARD ALLWORTH AND THE STUDY OF MODERN UZBEKS. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 303-308.
60. Sadullayev, U. (2024). ETHNOGENESIS AND ETHNIC HISTORY OF THE UZBEK PEOPLE. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 355-361.
61. Orifjonovich, O. A. . (2024). The Importance of Film Annotations in Analyzing Cinema Discourse. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION

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Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 5, 31 Май

- IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION, 4(3), 252–257. Retrieved from <https://inovatus.es/index.php/ejine/article/view/2711>
62. Ollomurodov, A. (2024). TRANSLATION FEATURES AND RESEARCH OF METAPHORS IN MODERN LINGUISTICS. MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH, 3(2), 821–828.
63. Orifjonovich, O. A. (2024). ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIKDA METAFORALARNING TARJIMA XUSUSIYATLARI VA TADQIQI.
64. Sulaymonovna, Q. N., & Orifjonovich, O. A. (2022). KONSEPTUAL METAFORALARNING LINGVOMADANIY HAMDA KOGNITIV XUSUSIYATLARI VA TIL TARAQQIYOTIDA TUTGAN ORNI. Scientific Impulse, 1(3), 594-600.
40. Sayfutdinov, F. (2023). ILLUMINATION OF KARAKALPAK PEOPLE IN ETHNOGRAPHIC STUDIES. Modern Science and Research, 2(12), 910–917. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/27281>
41. Ilniyoz o'g'li, S. F. (2023). XX ASR 2-YARMI XXI ASR BOSHLARI ZARAFSHON VOHASIDA ETNOSLARARO MUNOSABATLAR. TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 3(9), 1-5.
42. Sayfutdinov Feruz Ilniyozovich. (2023). STUDY OF THE KARAKALPAK PEOPLE IN ETHNOLOGICAL SCIENTIFIC WORKS HISTORY . International Journal Of History And Political Sciences, 3(12), 61–68. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ijhps/Volume03Issue12-11>
43. Sayfutdinov Feruz Ilniyoz o'g'li. (2023). XIX ASRDA XONLIKLARNING O'ZARO SAVDO MUNOSABATLARI. JOURNAL

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Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 5, 31 Май

OF SCIENCE, RESEARCH AND TEACHING, 2(8), 111–114. Retrieved from <http://jsrt.innovascience.uz/index.php/jsrt/article/view/284>

44. Sayfutdinov , F. (2024). ETHNIC COMPOSITION OF THE ZARAFSHAN OASIS (2ND HALF OF THE 20TH CENTURY). Modern Science and Research, 3(1), 577–581. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/28335>